

Soil resilience; Managing soil quality challenges in modern agriculture

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Introduction

Soil degradation

In India, soil degradation poses a serious challenge to environmental quality and agricultural sustainability in both irrigated and rain-fed agro-ecosystems (57% of the cultivated land). The result of such degradation is a perceived decline or stagnation in crop yield, partial factor productivity of inputs, and quality of the produce. Under intensive cropping systems, the main cause of yield drop is a decrease in SOM and the nutrients it is connected with in the soil (Muralidharudu *et al.*, 2011). The vital ecological functions of soil are harmed by these degrading forces and processes, which eventually affect the health/quality of the soil. The degree of degradation soil quality assessment, fitness for use, resilience "ability to recover," and identification of diagnostic recovery modules are the only solutions available to address this crucial problem for the sustainable use of soil and its protection against degradation (Fig. 1). For the purpose of identifying the most appropriate soil quality indicators, the idea of soil quality and the methods for evaluating it in relation to different soil functions have developed to a significant degree (Fig. 2). Although the indicators are used for soil quality monitoring (Andrews *et al.*, 2004), they have not yet been established for resilience purposes to evaluate the ease and degree of recovery of degraded systems (Kuan *et al.*, 2006).

Fig. 1: Land use management effect on soil resilience and degradation

Fig. 2: The concept of how soil resilience and resistance relate to soil quality through soil functions

Soil resilience

The ability of a soil to withstand or revert to its healthy state in the response of destabilizing forces is referred to as soil resilience. Some soils have the ability to regenerate on their own if the stress or disturbance is eliminated. The resilience of the soil determines ease of restoration, even

though specific treatments rely on soil and site characteristics. Restoring highly resilient soils is simple with the right management (Table 1). It is feasible to improve the conditions of resilient soils by using the land wisely and managing the soil carefully. Non-resilient soils may quickly lose their agronomic productivity below the economic level, even with enhanced systems of soil and crop management.

Table 1 Soil resilient classes

Class	Resilience	Description
0	Highly resilient	Quick recovery, high buffering
1	Resilient	Recovery with better management
2	Moderately resilient	Gradual recovery with high input
3	Slightly resilient	Delayed recovery despite changing land usage
4	Non-resilient	Even with a shift in land use, there is no recovery

The processes involved factors responsible and cause for soil resilience are presented diagrammatically. The concept of how soil resilience and resistance relate to soil quality through soil functions are described below in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Process, functions and causes for resilience

Role of soil resilience in soil degradation

According to theory, soil resilience is the ability of soil to regain its structural and functional integrity upon a disturbance (Lal, 1997). One of the major stresses and disruptions to the soil ecosystem is agriculture (Brussard, 1994). Although a conceptual framework for assessing soil resilience exists, there has only been a small amount of field level validation. Because both inherent and dynamic soil features have an impact on soil resilience and resistance (Fig. 5), there will be significant regional variation as well as changes in these factors with time and management techniques (Lal, 1998). Most soil functions will improve as a result of management strategies that raise soil organic matter levels (Fig. 4). Therefore, a protocol for assessing the soil resilience capacity of degraded soil with field level validation under various management interventions must be developed.

Fig. 4 Impact of soil functions on resilience (Ludwig et al., 2017)

Fig. 5: Main threats of soil resilience

Evaluation of soils for degradation and resilience

Demands for soil resources have increased due to an increase in human population, which is also a significant contributor to worldwide deforestation and the conversion of land to agriculture (Richards, 1990). Soils are increasingly used for the following things in addition to supplying food, fuel, fiber, and building materials. (i) Producing biomass for industrial use; (ii) bioremediation; (iii) preserving a large gene pool; (iv) engineering and military purposes; (v) aesthetic and cultural uses; and (vi) archaeological uses.

Fig. 5 Resilience and resistance of the soil microbial population affects how the soil ecosystem responds to disturbance (Griffith and Philippot, 2013)

Evaluation of soil degradation and resilience must take into account each of these functions. This effort aims to define research and development priorities for soil restoration and the enhancement of environmental quality. It also explains the fundamental concepts of soil resilience and degradation, describes the economic effects of soil degradation, and describes the methods for assessing and predicting soil resilience. Soil biota is a main driver of the interplay of soil properties with soil processes that build the natural capital of soils. Different soil functions are the result of this interplay. These functions together reflect the diversity of the soil response and functions, highlighting the system's resilience as a whole (Fig. 5).

Method for estimation of soil resilience

a) Assessment of soil quality index

Soil quality parameters were statistically tested for their level of significance. Only highly significant variables were subjected to Principal Component Analysis to derive minimum data sets which represents the appropriate quality indicators for SQI. The PCA which determine the MDS indicators, and they are converted to scores for better representation of values using linear or non linear scoring method (Andrews *et al.*, 2002; Brejeda *et al.*, 2002). Indicators are categorized into “good” or “bad” considering soil function. The SQI is calculated by considering weights calculated from each PC’s multiplying with scoring value. Weights is calculated by dividing cumulative variance of each PC with total variance of PC having eigen value >1.

$$SQI = \sum_{i=1}^n W_i S_i$$

Where, S_i is score, W_i is weightage factor

b) Soil resilience index

On the basis of soil quality index assessment data management interventions are selected. The resilience index (RI) of the soils of each of the selected sites after receiving management intervention is calculated using the following expression

$$RI = \frac{SQI(T) - SQI(d)}{SQI(p) - SQI(d)} \times 100,$$

Where, SQI (T): The SQI value of soil after management intervention (T)

SQI (d): The SQI value of soil before the management intervention (I)

SQI (p): The computed SQI value of pristine soil near the corresponding site.

The numerator in the above expression indicates the recovery of SQI value due to management intervention whereas the denominator indicates the loss of SQI value due to soil degradation processes.

c) Assessment of the rate of soil degradative process

To evaluate the relative resilience of the soil, one might measure the rate of soil degradation under a certain ecological stress. These pressures include changes in soil chemical and nutritional composition, porosity, clay and colloid content, and rate of soil erosion.

$$Sr = -dS_q/dt$$

S_q is soil quality and t is time

d) Assessment of the rate of soil restoration

$$Sr = dS_q/dt$$

e) Modelling

Temporal changes in soil quality and soil resilience can be modelled

- ✓ Soil renewal rate,
- ✓ Physical analogue,
- ✓ Capacity to withstand stress,
- ✓ Characteristic return time

Conclusion

Soil quality is assessed integrating physical, chemical and biological attributes of soils. These characteristics may alter as a result of different management techniques and cropping patterns, which could improve or deteriorate soil quality. The conceptual framework for evaluating soil resilience has been designed with field level validation. The method described here for measuring soil resilience can successfully be used to measure the resilience power of degraded soils in response to management interventions.

References

- Andrews, S. S., Karlen, D. L., Cambardella, C. A., 2004. The soil management assessment framework: a quantitative soil quality evaluation method. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*, 68, 1945-1962.
- Andrews, S.S., Karlen, D.L., Mitchell, J.P., 2002. A comparison of soil quality indexing methods for vegetable systems in Northern California. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 90, 25-45.
- Brejeda, J. J, Moorman, T. B., Karlen, D.L., Dao, T. H., 2000. Identification of regional soil quality factors and indicators. Central and southern high plains. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 64, 2115-2124.
- Brussard, L. 1994. Interrelationships between biological activities, soil properties and soil management. In *Soil Resilience and Sustainable Land Use*, eds. D.J. Greenland and I. Szabolcs, 309-352, CAB Int. Wallingford, Oxon, UK.
- Kuan, H. L., Hallett, P. D., Griffiths, B. S., Gregory, A. S., Watts, C. W. and Whitmore, A. P., 2006. The biological and physical stability and resilience of a selection of Scottish soils to stresses. *European Journal of Soil Science* 58(3): 811-821.
- Lal, R. 1997. Degradation and resilience of soils. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London B* 352: 997-1008.
- Lal, R. 1998. Soil quality and sustainability. In *Methods for Assessment of Soil Degradation*, eds. W.H. Blum, C. Valentine and B.A. Stewart, 17-30, CRC Press, Boca raton, FL.
- Griffiths, B. S. and Philippot, L., 2013, Insights into the resistance and resilience of the soil microbial community. *FEMS Microbiol. Rev.* 37: 112–129.
- Muralidharudu, Y, Mandal, B. N., Reddy, S. K., Rao, S. A., 2011, In: *Progress Report of the All India Coordinated Research Project for Investigation on soil test crop response correlation*, Indian Institute of Soil Science, Bhopal, 11-61.